

3,4-Coumarinopyrones. Part II. Synthesis of Some Coumarino-(3',4'-5, 6)- α -Pyrones

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Coumarino-(3', 4', 5, 6) α -pyrone derivatives have been synthesised by the Pechmann condensation of a number of 4-hydroxycoumarins with β -ketoic esters. Some of these coumarinopyrones have been degraded by the action of alkali in an interesting manner. The mechanism for degradation is explained. A few 4-hydroxycoumarins have also been synthesised.

Synthesis of coumarino-(3',4',-5,6)- α -pyrones by the Pechmann condensation of some 4-hydroxycoumarins with β -ketoic esters was reported in our previous communication.¹ In extension of the same 4-hydroxy-8-isopropyl-5-methylcoumarin(IIa) and 4-hydroxy-5,6-benzocoumarin(IV) have been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ to afford coumarino(3',4'-5,6)-4,5'-dimethyl-8'-isopropyl- α -pyrone (IIIa, Y=H) and benzo(5',6') coumarino-(3', 4',-5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrone (V, Y=H) respectively. Optimum yields (as high as 70%) were obtained when the coumarin derivative, β -ketoic ester, and anhydrous $AlCl_3$ were used in the molar proportion of 1:3:2. Excess of β -ketoic ester was found to be very essential for obtaining good yields. The same coumarino- α -pyrones, but in very poor yields, were obtained with H_2SO_4 and $POCl_3$ as condensing agents. Condensation of products(IIa) and (IV) with ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ furnished the coumarino- α -pyrones (IIIa, Y=Me) and (V, Y=Me) respectively.

(I)

(II)

(III)

a: $R_1=CHMe_2$; $R_2=H$; $R_3=Me$. b: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$; $R_3=Me$. c: $R_1=Et$; $R_2=Me$; $R_3=H$. d: $R_1=CHMe_2$; $R_2=Br$; $R_3=Me$.

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

1. Patell and Usgaonkar, this *Journal*, 1966, 42, 215.

These coumarino- α -pyrones showed good stability towards aqueous NaOH. The coumarino (3',4'-5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrones, studied previously, were degraded by boiling with 20% aqueous NaOH to furnish the corresponding salicylic acid derivatives¹, but the coumarino- α -pyrone (IIIa: Y=H) was recovered unchanged after refluxing it with 20% aqueous NaOH for 3hr. and acidifying the resulting solution. It degraded itself partially by refluxing it with 50% aqueous NaOH for 3 hr. On acidifying the resulting solution, a mixture of the unchanged coumarino- α -pyrone, 4-hydroxy-8-isopropyl-5-methylcoumarin (IIa), and an unidentified oily substance was obtained. The mixture was separated (vide experimental) and the first two substances were identified by taking mixed m.p. with the authentic specimens. Analysis of the oil (unidentified) by TLC on silica gel using benzene-petroleum (30:20) phase indicated that it was a mixture of three or four substances. The separation of the components of this oil could not be undertaken on account of its very small quantity.

The stability of this coumarino- α -pyrone (IIIa, Y=H) towards alkali may be explained as due to presence of -Me group in position 5 of the coumarino-pyrone molecule, the steric effect of which makes the nucleophilic attack of -OH difficult on the adjacent $>C=O$ group of the molecule formed after opening of the ring (see Mechanism II, B). It is this attack which can be expected to lead to the degradation of the coumarino- α -pyrones, reported previously to provide salicylic acid derivatives¹, as shown in Mechanism I.

Mechanism I

Formation of a small amount of 4-hydroxy-8-isopropyl-4-methylcoumarin (IIa) as degradation product of the coumarino- α -pyrone (IIIa, Y=H) by the action of 50% aqueous NaOH may be explained by mechanism (II) formulated below. In this case, because of the steric effect of -Me group in position 5' of the coumarino-pyrone(IIIa) which shields the $>C=O$ group (formed after opening of the pyrone rings (II, B) from nucleophilic attack, the nucleophile ($\bar{O}H$) chooses probably, the less reactive site of α - β unsaturated carboxylated group $-C=CH-CO\bar{O}$, β carbon atom of it is sufficiently electron-deficient for the attack of nucleophilic $\bar{O}H$ due to (i) combined inductive and mesomeric effect of $-CO\bar{O}$ at the end of chain and (ii) inductive effect of powerfully electron attracting

the carbanion that is formed takes up the proton from adjacent-OH. This leads to the rupture of C-C bond as shown in(II, D.) This rupture is further facilitated due to -I effect of neighbouring COO^- group. The resulting compound then undergoes again the nucleophilic attack, by HO^- (II, F), leading finally to elimination of $-C-Me$. The resulting compound

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then undergoes cyclisation on acidification(II, S) to provide 4-hydroxycoumarin derivative (IIIa).

Mechanism II

Benzo(5',6')-coumarino(3', 4'-5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrone (V) also showed good stability towards alkali. It became degraded partially by boiling it with 20% aqueous NaOH for 3 hr. to afford 1-acetyl-2-naphthol (VI) which was identified by mixed m.p. determination with an authentic specimen, prepared by Fries migration of β -naphthyl acetate according to Imoto². Incidentally, most of the coumarino- α -pyrone (V, Y = H) was recovered unchanged after acidification. Stability of the benzocoumarino- α -pyrone to the alkali and its degradation to 1-acetyl-2-naphthol (VI) may be attributed to the steric effect of the benzene ring in 5- and 6-position of the coumarino-pyrone molecule which shields the adjoining-C- (group formed after opening of the ring) from the nucle-

philic attack and thus prevents degradation by mechanism I. The degradation then follows the course shown in mechanism II by choosing less reactive site for the attack. In the last stage (II, T), decarboxylation probably takes place readily, thus leading to the formation of 1-acetyl-2-naphthol (VI) instead of cyclodehydration to 4-hydroxycoumarin derivative.

4-Hydroxy-8-ethyl-5-methylcoumarin (IIb), 4-hydroxy-8-ethyl-6-methylcoumarin (IIc), and 4-hydroxy-6-bromo-8-isopropyl-5-methylcoumarin (IIId) were synthesised in good yields by condensing the phenols (Ib), (Ic) and (Id) respectively, with malonic acid using the mixture of POCl_3 and fused ZnCl_2 as condensing agent. Condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarins (IIb), (IIc) and (IIId) with ethyl acetoacetate took place smoothly in presence of anhydrous AlCl_3 to furnish the corresponding coumarino (3',4'-5,6)- α -

pyrone derivatives, viz: (IIIb), (IIIc) and (IIIId)(Y=H) respectively. All the coumarino- α -pyrones dissolved in aqueous NaOH (10%) on warming on a water bath and were regenerated unchanged on acidification.

FIG 1.

U.V. absorption curves of the coumarino(3',4'—5,6)- α -pyrones are recorded in Fig. 1 and 2 above. Peaks between 255 and 280 $m\mu$ and between 335 and 350 $m\mu$ with λ_{max} at about 280-90 $m\mu$ are characteristics of these coumarino-pyrone.

EXPERIMENTAL

Coumarino(3',4'-5,6)-4,5'-dimethyl-8'-isopropyl- α pyrone (IIIa, Y=H)

(i) In presence of Anhydrous $AlCl_3$:—4-Hydroxy-8-isopropyl-5-methylcoumarin¹⁰ (IIa) (4.4 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (7.8 g.) were added to a solution of anhydrous $AlCl_3$

8. Shah et al., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 677; also V. R. Shah, Ph. D. thesis 1959, Bombay Univ.

(5.4 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (24 ml); the mixture was heated at 130° for about 4 hr. It was decomposed by adding crushed ice and HCl. (conc.) and nitrobenzene was removed by steam

FIG. 2

distillation. The residual solid was triturated with NaHCO_3 solution to remove unchanged coumarin and then it was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 179-80°, yield 4.0 g. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 5.7. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6%). U.V. absorption in MeOH λ_{MAX} : 270, 335 and 345 m μ (log ϵ , 4.03, 4.17 and 4.12).

When the condensation was carried out using less amount of ethyl acetoacetate (1M, 2.8 g.), the yield of the coumarino- α -pyrone (IIIa, Y=H) was 2.2 g.

(ii) *In presence of H_2SO_4 .*—The coumarin (IIa) (2.2 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (4g.) and H_2SO_4 (7ml, 80%) were mixed together and the mixture after keeping at the room temperature for 48 hr. was poured on crushed ice. The solid product was triturated with NaHCO_3 solution to remove unchanged coumarin. The insoluble product was crystal-

lised from benzene in needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, 179-80°, yield 0.13 g. The unchanged coumarin(IIa) was recovered by acidification of the filtrate; recovered yield, 1.5 g.

(iii) *In presence of POCl₃*.—The coumarin IIa (1.4 g.) ethyl acetoacetate (2.4 g.) and POCl₃ (3 ml.), were mixed together and the mixture was heated at 70-75° for 4 hr. and then poured on crushed ice. The sticky product was washed repeatedly with aqueous NaHCO₃ (by trituration), then washed with water, dried, crystallised from benzene in plates; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 179-80°; yield, 0.1 g.

Action of Aqueous NaOH on the Coumarino- α -pyrone(IIIa, Y=H).—The coumarino- α -pyrone (4 g.) was mixed with aqueous NaOH (40ml, 50%) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hr. On cooling, an oily substance separated. It dissolved on adding few ml. of water to the reaction mixture, forming a clear solution. This was acidified with HCl and was left overnight. The precipitated solid was then triturated with aqueous NaOH(10%). The insoluble residue (1.0 g.) was the unchanged coumarino- α -pyrone. It was crystallised from benzene in needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen, 179-80°. The solution was acidified and extracted with ether. The ether extract was shaken with aqueous NaHCO₃ two or three times and the extract on acidification furnished 4-hydroxy-8-isopropyl-5-methylcoumarin (IIa). It was crystallised from methanol in plates; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen, 223-24°. After removing ether from the ether extract, a small amount of the oil remained behind. It showed a bluish green colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. TLC of the oil over silica gel, using benzene-petroleum (30:20) phase, showed four spots, indicating presence of four compounds.

Coumarino(3',4',5,6)-8'-isopropyl-3,4,5'-trimethyl- α -pyrone (IIIa Y=Me)
A mixture of the coumarin (IIa) (2.2 g.) ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate (4.3 g.) anhydrous AlCl₃ (2.6 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (12 ml) was heated at 130° for 4 hr. and the reaction mixture was worked out as in case of (IIIa, Y=H). The sticky product, after washing with dilute alkali solution (by trituration) and water was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 165-66°, yield, 0.52 g. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 5.9. C₁₈H₁₈O₄ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.0%)

Benzo (5',6') coumarino (3',4',5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrone(V, Y=H):—4-Hydroxy-5,6-benzocoumarin⁵ (IV) (4.3 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (7.8 g.) and anhydrous AlCl₃ (5.4 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (24 ml) were mixed together and heated at 130° for 4 hr. and then worked up as usual. The product was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 245-46° yield 3.6 g. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 3.8. C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 73.4; H, 3.6%) U. V. absorption: λ_{max}^{MeOH} 265, 275, 375 and 395 (log ϵ , 4.16, 4.13, 4.32 & 4.18). When ethyl acetoacetate (1M 2.8 g.) was used in the above reaction, the yield of (V, Y=H) was 2 g.

The condensation of (IV) (2.1 g.) with ethyl acetoacetate (4 g.) in presence of 80% H₂SO₄ (7ml) as in previous case, furnished the same coumarino- α -pyrone; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 245-46°, yield 0.02 g. Product (IV) recovered was 1.3 g.

The condensation of (IV)(1.3 g) with ethyl acetoacetate (2.4 g) in presence of POCl₃ (3 ml), as in previous case, furnished also (V, Y=H), m.p. and mixed m.p. with previous specimen 245-46°, yield 0.04 g.

Action of NaOH on the Benzocoumarino- α -pyrone(V, Y=H).—The benzocoumarino- α -pyrone (V: Y=H) (3 g.) was refluxed with 20% aqueous NaOH (30 ml) for 3 hr. On

cooling the solution, sodium salt separated. It was filtered and dissolved in minimum quantity of water. On acidifying this solution, a oily substance separated. It was taken in ether. After removing the ether, it slowly solidified on scratching. It was crystallised from petrolcum (40-60°) in plates, m.p. 65-67°. It developed a reddish brown colour with EtOH-FeCl₃. It was identified as 1-acetyl-2-naphthol by taking mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen (prepared by the Fries migration of β -naphthyl-acetate according to Imoto⁶) which showed no depression. Unchanged benzocoumarino- α -pyrone (V, Y=H) (0.4 g.) was recovered on acidification of the alkali filtrate. It was crystallised from benzene in needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen 245-46°.

Benzo (5',6')-coumarino(3',4'-5,6)-3,4-dimethyl- α -pyrone (V, Y=Me) was prepared by heating together the benzocoumarin (IV) (2.1 g.), ethyl- α -methylacetoacetate (4.4 g.), and anhydrous AlCl₃ (2.7 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (12ml) at 130° as usual. The product, after washing with dilute alkali was crystallised from acetic acid (charcoal) in yellowish needles m.p. 269-70°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 3.9. C₁₉H₁₄O₄ requires C, 73.0; H, 4.1%).

8-Ethyl 4 hydroxy 5-methylcoumarin (IIb):—2-Ethyl-5-methylphenol⁴ (Ib) (6.8 g.) malonic acid (5.2 g.), fused ZnCl₂ (20.5 g.), and POCl₃ (23 ml) were mixed together and the mixture was heated at 60-65° for 18hr. Crushed ice was then added and the sticky paste separating was boiled with fresh water for few minutes and was then dissolved in a saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ solution by boiling. The solution was cooled and the insoluble material was removed by filtration. The sticky product, obtained after acidification of the solution, was crystallised from methanol (charcoal) in needles, m.p. 232-34° (decomp.), yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 5.5. C₁₈H₁₄O₃ requires C, 70.6. H, 5.0%).

Coumarino(3',4'-5,6)-4,5'-dimethyl-8'-ethyl- α -pyrone (IIIb, Y=H):—The coumarin (IIb) (0.5 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (0.8 g.), and anhydrous AlCl₃ (0.6 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (2.5 ml) were mixed together and heated at 130° for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was worked out as usual. The product after washing with dilute alkali was crystallised from benzene-petroleum mixture in needles, m.p. 182-83°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 71.1; H, 5.0. C₁₆H₁₄O₄ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2%). U.V. absorption: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{M-OH}}$ 242, 270, 333 and 350 (log ϵ , 3.92, 4.12, 4.12 & 4.12).

2-Ethyl-4-methylphenol (Ic) was prepared by the Clemmenson reduction of 2-acetyl-5-methylphenol⁵ (40 g.) by refluxing it with zinc amalgam (from 100 g. of zinc dust) and HCl (1:1, 200 ml) for about 5 hr. with addition of HCl (1:1) from time to time. In all about 600 ml of HCl (1:1) was consumed. The oil separating on cooling was collected, washed with water, and dried. It distilled at 217-20°, yield 29 g. Ungano and McLaron⁶ who prepared it by hydrogenation of 2-acetyl-5-methylphenol over Raney Nickel, reported b.p. 215-221°.

8-Ethyl-4-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin (IIc):—A mixture of 2-ethyl-4-methylphenol (Ic) (20.4 g.), malonic acid (20.8 g.), fused ZnCl₂ (82 g.) and POCl₃ (82 ml) was heated at 70-75° for 15 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described under (IIb). The coumarin crystallised from methanol in stout needles, m.p. 215-16° yield 12 g. (Found: C, 70.9; H, 6.0. C₁₈H₁₄O₃ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%).

4. Uegonkar et al., this Journal, 1953, 30, 785.

5. Rosenmund and Sebnurr, Annalen, 1928, 460, 50.

Coumarino (3',4'-5,6)-4,6'-dimethyl-8'-ethyl- α -pyrone (IIIc, Y=H):—The coumarin (IIc) (4 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (7.8 g.), and anhydrous AlCl_3 (5.4 g) in dry nitrobenzene (24 ml) were heated together as usual at 130° for 4 hr. and the reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product after washing with aqueous NaHCO_3 was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. $165\text{--}06^\circ$, yield 3.2 g. (Found: C 71.4; H, 5.4. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.1 and H, 5.2%). U.V. absorption: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 270, 335, 351 (log ϵ , 4.00, 3.96 and 4.00).

6-Bromo-4-hydroxy-8-isopropyl-5-methylcoumarin (IIId):—A mixture of 4-bromothymol (7g.) malonic acid (3.3 g.), anhydrous ZnCl_2 (13 g.) and POCl_3 (15 ml) was heated at $70\text{--}75^\circ$ for 6 hr. and the reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice. The pasty product was boiled with water for 1/2 hr. and then was repeatedly crystallised from methanol (charcoal) in stout needles, m. p. $268\text{--}69^\circ$, yield, 1 g. (Found: C, 53.0; H, 4.1; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3$, Br requires C, 52.5 H, 4.4.%)

Coumarino (3',4'-5,6) -6'-bromo-4,5'-dimethyl-8'-isopropyl- α -pyrone (IIIId, Y=H) was prepared in the usual manner by heating together the coumarin (IIId) (0.6 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (0.8 g.) and anhydrous AlCl_3 (0.6 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (2.5 ml) at 130° . The product, after washing with dilute alkali NaOH (by trituration) was crystallised from benzene in plates m.p. $205\text{--}06^\circ$, yield 0.52 g. (Found: C, 56.3, H, 4.0. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4$, Br requires C, 56.2; H, 4.1%).

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